

Relative Probabilities in Quantum and Classical Statistical Mechanics

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Classical mechanics in the ideal gas scenario and quantum mechanics make use of a set of energy levels which a single particle may occupy. Thus the problem becomes to determine the probability associated with e_i i.e. $P(e_i)$. In this note we take the approach that relative probabilities depend on the energy gap in question. For example, consider a quantum two level system where e_i values are provided by the time-independent Schrodinger equation. From the point of view of statistics, these are simply a set of e_i values. Their associated physics is contained in the Schrodinger equation. For the quantum two level system one must find the relative probabilities $PR(e_1)$ and $PR(e_2)$. Next, imagine a quantum system with many levels and assume for the sake of argument there are levels e_1, e_2 and $e_i, e_{(i+1)}$ such that $e_2 - e_1 = e_{(i+1)} - e_i$. If the mechanism is the same for jumping from e_1 to e_2 and from e_i to $e_{(i+1)}$ (i.e. absorbing a photon of the same energy), one might argue that the relative probabilities $PR(e_2)/PR(e_1) = PR(e_{(i+1)})/PR(e_i)$. From this one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann result $\exp(-e_i/T)$. Note that levels do not need to be adjacent. For example in a large level system one might consider e_1 and e_3 and any e_i and e_j such that $e_3 - e_1 = e_j - e_i$.

In some situations this may need to be modified (e.g. fermions and bosons have enhancements and there may be level related issues), but as a first step we argue that insisting on relative probabilities being dependent on $e_i - e_j$ has important consequences. Furthermore, in such a case the normalization constant for these relative probabilities i.e. $C(T) = \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T)$ is important. Taking $\ln(C(T))$ and then taking the derivative d/dT yields an expression proportional to the average energy. An expression for dE/dT , however, would lead to a second order differential equation in $\ln(C(T))$. If one introduces a new function S such that $E - TS = -T \ln(C)$, then one may show that $dE/dT = T dS/dT$ i.e. entropy S emerges.

Relative Probabilities and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

Consider the wavefunction: $W(x,t) = \sqrt{b} \exp(-iE_1 t) W_1(x) + \sqrt{1-b} \exp(-iE_2 t) W_2(x)$ ((1)). There are probabilities $b=P(e_1)$ and $1-b=P(e_2)$, but b is unknown. Imagine this wavefunction is linked to a photon bath which supplies photons with energy $e_2 - e_1$. One may consider an equilibrium occurring with $P(e_1/T)$ and $P(e_2/T)$ where T is a parameter linked to average energy, but also one which makes e_1/T dimensionless.

Next consider $W(x,t) = \sum_i a_i(E_i) \exp(-E_i t) W_i(x)$ ((2)). Imagine also that $e_2 - e_1 = e_{i+1} - e_i$ for a given i . In other words there are two two level systems which seem identical (in terms of energy gap). Thus a photon with energy $e_2 - e_1$ might excite either e_1 or e_i with equal probability. (One may imagine physical situations where the energy level might possibly affect the interaction with the photon, but for the simplest case assume a given photon may just as easily excite e_1 as e_i .) If one has equilibrium, one might argue that in terms of relative probabilities the two two level systems should be identical i.e.

$$PR(e_2)/PR(e_1) = PR(e_{(i+1)}) / PR(e_i) = f(e_2 - e_1) \quad ((3))$$

If one sets $e_2 = y + dy$ and $e_1 = y$ then: $PR(y + dy) = PR(y) f(dy)$ ((4))

((3)) implies a solution is $PR(e) = a^e$ ((5)). Thus $f(dy)$ becomes $PR(dy)$.

((5)) may be rewritten as $PR(e) = \exp(-e/T)$ ((6)) to ensure that for large e , probability goes to zero.

Idea of Indistinguishability in Equilibrium

The idea of equilibrium seems to be linked to indistinguishability in certain degrees of freedom. For example, for a gas in a box with no potential one spatial position is as good as the other and so density is constant. Furthermore average energy for an ideal gas is the same at each point i.e. proportional to T , otherwise a specific point would be given preference. For elastic two body scattering $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 = e$, product probabilities do not distinguish between e_i and e_j as long as $e_i + e_j = e$. This approach also yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ as $PR(e_i)PR(e_j) = \text{constant}$ depending on e . Thus one expects $PR(e_i)PR(e_j) = PR(e_i + e_j)$.

In the previous section we argue that if the same energy gap exists between levels (even if they are not adjacent) they have the same relative probability $PR(e_j)PR(e_i)$ which also suggests the Maxwell-Boltzmann form.

Importance of the Normalization Constant

If the relative probability for an energy state e_i is $\exp(-e_i/T)$ where T determines the average energy, then the normalization constant:

$$C(T) = \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((7))$$

becomes important because it characterizes the overall system. The relative probabilities $\exp(-e_i/T)$ are the same for any system (which has the same probability for any $e_j - e_i = \text{constant}$ jump (photon/phonon absorption etc.)

By examining $C(T)$ one may see that it is closely linked to average energy because d/dT brings in $-e_i/T$. In fact, introducing $\ln(C(T))$ allows one to link a relative probability with the normalization $C(T)$ when taking d/dT . Thus:

$$d/dT \ln(C(T)) = 1/(TT) \sum_i e_i \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((8))$$

If one defines a function S such that $E - TS = -T \ln(C(T))$ then a solution for S is immediately:

$$S = - \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i)) \quad \text{where } P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)/C(T)$$

In other words, one piece of $\ln(P(e_i))$ yields $-e_i/T$ while the other yields $-\ln(C)$. $\ln(C)$ is system specific, e.g. for a two level system it contains e_1 and e_2 . e_i/T , however, is generic as T is only a

parameter and e_i might exist in any system. This is needed because average energy $\sum_i e_i P(e_i)$ contains a generic piece e_i (from the point of view of statistics) and $P(e_i)$ which is system specific because it contains $C(T)$. One may note that one needs to multiply S by T to remove $1/T$ in $-e_i/T$.

One may ask why the function S is introduced? From ((8)) one may see that:

$$dE/dT dT = d/dT \{ T T d/dT \ln(C) \} \quad ((9))$$

This leads to a second order differential equation whereas it may be shown that S leads to a first order one, namely:

$$dE = T dS \quad \text{or} \quad dE/dT dT = T dS/dT dT \quad ((10))$$

Thus entropy and its \ln form follow from the \ln form of $\ln(C(T))$ where $C(T)$ is the relative probability normalization and \ln allows for $d/dT \ln(C(T))$ to bring down $1/C(T)$ so that one has a result proportional to average energy. S allows one to have a linear equation $dE=TdS$ where $dE=dE/dT dT$. In other words parameters like L the length of a box with infinite potential walls in quantum mechanics are kept constant because in that case $e_i=\text{constant } n/LL$. This we argue is an alternative way in which to see entropy emerge.

Level Dependent Effects

It is possible to modify the above to include level dependent effects. For example, for fermions one may only have one in each e_i state which also includes spin i.e. e_i spin up would be a state. Furthermore, there may be level dependent effects on photon absorption which would modify matters also, although the form $\exp(-e_i/T)$ may still emerge modified by a factor $f(e_i)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in equilibrium one seeks possible indistinguishable features. Imagine a system of many energy levels. If two levels e_1 and e_2 have an energy gap of e_2-e_1 , then there may be two other levels e_j and e_i such that $e_j-e_i=e_2-e_1$. In such a case one may argue that these are indistinguishable to photon emission or absorption (assuming this is also the case in nature). One might argue that relative probabilities are the same i.e. $PR(e_2)/PR(e_1) = PR(e_j)/PR(e_i)$. From this we argue that a solution is $PR(e)=\exp(-e/T) = \text{number to the power of } e$. As a result, the normalization constant $C(T)=\sum_i \exp(-e_i/T)$ becomes important. One may show that $E_{ave} = T T d/dT \ln(C(T))$. In such a case $dE_{ave}/dT dT$ leads to a second order differential equation in $\ln(C(T))$. If one introduces a function S such that $E-TS = -T \ln(C)$ then one may show that $S=-\sum_i P(e_i)\ln(P(e_i))$ and that $dE=TdS$ (for a change in T holding mechanical parameters such as the length of a quantum box with infinite potential walls constant).